

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

Recommended citation of this article

Schoneberger, C. (2011). Adult Literacy Instruction in Germany: Issues and Challenges. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 6(1), 79–88.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8004277>

Citation for LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

This article is part of a collection of articles based on presentations from the 2010 Symposium held at University of Cologne in Cologne, Germany. Please note that the year of publication is often different than the year the symposium was held. We recommend the following citation when referencing the edited collection.

Schöneberger, C., van de Craats, I., & Kurvers, J. (Eds.) (2011). Low-educated adult second language and literacy Acquisition (LESLLA): Proceedings of the 6th symposium. Centre for Language Studies.
<https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org/index.php/lesllasp/issue/view/471>

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ADULT LITERACY INSTRUCTION IN GERMANY: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Christiane Schöneberger, University of Cologne

1 *Introduction*

During the United Nations Literacy Decade from 2003 to 2012, the field of adult literacy instruction has received renewed attention in Germany. The German government has announced basic education and social participation as two major goals in the field, especially in the context of immigration politics and changes in the educational system. The present paper presents some of the fundamental issues and challenges that arise, especially regarding the education of literacy teachers as well as regarding class policies for the assessment of learners' oral and literate skills in German as a Second Language (GSL).

2 *(Il)literacy in Germany: the status quo*

Although adult literacy instruction has been recognized as an educational and political challenge in Germany since the 1970s, it has not attracted much systematic qualitative or quantitative research to date. Schramm & Roll (2010: 5) point out that this research is starting to be carried out only now, much delayed, which is due to the longstanding socio-political and academic marginalization of the field. The recent efforts in investigating the illiteracy situation in Germany both socio-politically and scientifically are a consequence of an initiative of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, taken in the context of the current United Nations Literacy Decade. The Ministry has declared literacy and basic education for adults as one focal point of academic and educational interest and has provided financial funding for 24 research groups in the field. The general aims of these projects are: improving the current state of research, increasing participation of adults in education and facilitating access to literacy instruction, improving policies in teaching, assessing and counseling, professionalizing and improving teacher education and, finally, interconnecting research and practice (cf. Alphabund, 2010). The research projects are taking place between 2007 and 2012, hence, providing an empirically corroborated, complete picture of the (il)literacy situation in Germany with its numerous facets is not yet possible, but first results are starting to become available.

Schöneberger, van de Craats and Kurvers
LESLLA Proceedings 2010

In addition, it is hard to get hold of definite numbers representing the illiteracy situation in Germany. First, official statistics often do not differentiate between native speakers of German who left school without adequate literacy skills and immigrants that do not have sufficient literacy skills in GSL, but who may or may not have them in their native language. The latter group, i.e. immigrant learners, however, is by far the majority among illiterate learners in Germany. It is also an especially heterogeneous group because the native languages of immigrants as well as their degree of education in the native language differ, as do their oral skills in German and their time spans of residence in Germany and exposure to the German L2. It is therefore not infrequent that there are learners in L2 literacy classes that are, in fact, literate and adequately educated in their first language and could be alphabetized in GSL easily, if only their oral skills in GSL could be improved. This seems to be especially true of learners whose L1 uses a writing system that is different from that of German, such as Chinese or Russian. At the same time, these groups may also have learners with no prior schooling at all who are, in fact, primarily illiterate, i.e. they cannot read and write in any language and have to start from the absolute beginning, e.g. learning the alphabet.

In the large group of immigrant learners that are regarded as 'illiterate', insufficient oral skills in L2 German are often confounded with insufficient reading and writing skills. Additionally, learners of very diverse backgrounds and levels of proficiency are instructed together, which puts the instructors in a very challenging and difficult position, because they have to find the right teaching contents and methods for each individual learner. These instructors often report that instead of teaching a group of learners, they teach "twelve private lessons at the same time" (oral communication with a GSL literacy instructor). This is aggravated by the fact that the situation of instructors and teachers in the field is problematic also in terms of their professional education as well as in terms of occupational and financial conditions.

Finally, the diagnostic tools that exist for the assessment and evaluation of learners' existing oral and literate skills are insufficient and, in particular, they are not suitable for the ascertained degrees of diversity and heterogeneity that are the rule, rather than the exception, in literacy classes.

2.1 Facts and figures

In March 2011, the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research has published a study by the University of Hamburg that puts the number of illiterate persons in Germany at 7.5 million. The study investigated adults in the age range 18-64.¹ That represents an illiteracy rate among these adults of approx. 14.5%. This is a situation that Peter Hubertus, Director of the German Federal Association of Alphabetization and Basic Education (Bundesverband Alphabetisierung und Grundbildung e.V.), calls 'alarming' and 'requiring immediate action' (Bundesverband Alphabetisierung, 2011).

¹ The study is limited to this age range because it represents the group of potential employees who cannot be integrated in the job market because of their limited literacy skills. It should be pointed out that according to the current literacy policy in Germany, economic aims like employment and long-term integration in the job market are the strongest motivation for providing literacy instruction (cf. Schramm & Roll, 2010: 6).

According to the recent study by the University of Hamburg, an adult is regarded as being "functionally illiterate" if s/he is unable to participate actively and appropriately in society as a consequence of his/her limited literacy skills (Grothlüschen & Riekmann, 2011: LEO or Level One Studie). Social participation, hence, is a principal yardstick for the evaluation of illiteracy. This notion contains most importantly employment in the German job market, but also participation in the educational system and participation in social activities such as clubs, associations and societies, among other aspects.

The Level-One study examined literacy skills of adults on the lowest levels, hence level one. It differentiates between subjects whose literacy skills are below word level, below sentence level or below text level. These three subgroups represent the group of "functionally illiterate" persons and sum up to the percentage of 14.5%. This figure does not include those adults in the investigated age range that are not strictly illiterate, but have severe difficulties with orthography and spelling and whose literacy skills resemble (or are below) those of a primary school kid. This group constitutes an additional 25.9% of adults between 18 and 64, according to LEO.

Of the 14.5% of people who are functionally illiterate in the narrow sense (i. e. below, word, sentence or text level), 60.3% are men and 39.7% are women. Dividing the subjects into groups of smaller age ranges, a slight trend can be observed of illiteracy rates rising with age: the age group 18-29 contains 19.9% of subjects, as compared to 20.6% in the range 30-39, 27.0% in the range 40-49 and 32.6% in the range 50-64. This suggests that the type of illiteracy investigated in the study might be dependent on age-correlating factors, such as time spent in school etc. This, however, needs further investigation.

It has to be noted that the only piece of information that the study provides with regard to the native language context is limited to a differentiation between L1 and L2 speakers of German. According to LEO, 58.1% of the investigated functionally illiterate subjects speak German as their first language while 41.8% speak German as their second language. Immigrants who have no or very limited oral skills in L2 German are not included in these figures. This procedure clearly points to one of the biggest challenges in literacy practice and policy in Germany: who has access to literacy education and, more importantly, who is excluded from it and for what reasons?

2.2 Barriers to literacy education

It is an apparent paradox that while low-educated immigrants with insufficient GSL literacy skills represent the largest group of illiterate learners in Germany, it is not consistently this group that receives the greatest political attention and support. Although the funding for literacy classes for immigrants is better than for German native speakers, the decision who is assigned to a literacy course is often related to perspectives of employment and integration in the job market. This is evident in the current policy of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research which has recently announced a new focal point of interest in the context of literacy instruction: literacy instruction in economy and employment. This means that primarily learners who are potentially relevant for the employment market receive access to literacy instruction, i.e. younger learners who have had (or are currently engaged in) professional training of some kind and who promise to be placeable in a job later on.

This practice excludes senior learners, immigrants with no work permit, housewives with no prior job training etc. It is not the case, however, that these groups cannot attend a literacy class. But in contrast to the first group of “potentially employable learners”, they do not receive financial or other support (such as child care during class time, free public transport etc.).

A second barrier to literacy education is constructed by the social context and living conditions of immigrant learners, in particular. It is often the case that these learners prefer to remain in their familiar neighborhoods. Leaving their accustomed residential area and commuting to another part of town for the literacy class often means an insurmountable, worry-afflicted challenge for them. PAGES² project work over the last three years has shown that having to leave the area in order to obtain literacy instruction leads to higher drop-out rates, while these immigrant learners (mostly low-educated women living in traditional family structures and with no or very little prior schooling) are happy to attend a literacy class in their own neighborhood. This barrier could easily be dismantled if literacy instruction was offered in the home territory of these learners, e.g. in local social services institution, their children’s schools, community halls etc. Such decentralized instruction, however, means a greater organizational and administrative challenge for the educational provider and hence, class offers of this kind are rare.

Finally, another barrier for access to literacy education lies in the learners’ prior schooling experience. This is especially the case for those learners who have attended school and have left it without sufficient levels of literacy proficiency. Their motivation to attend another school-like class context is low. Feelings of frustration and disappointment often prevent these learners from making another attempt to learn. Traditional literacy classes often confront these learners with the same types of tasks, exercises and teaching methods that they have experienced in school and that have failed for them. Therefore, it can help these learners to engage them in learning contexts that make use of alternative curricula. Pilot projects have tried to do this and have offered cooking lessons, computer classes, drama groups etc. where the focus is on another content than learning to read and write and where literacy instruction is sneaked in through a detour. Results from these attempts show that learning results are good, the drop-out rates are low and, most importantly, learners often do not realize that they are being instructed in literacy, because their focus is on learning to handle a computer or performing a play.

Although it will probably be a long way to the establishment of such class offers on a regular basis and to their region-wide implementation, all these findings are promising first steps on the way to increased access to literacy instruction and improved class offers.

² PAGES (to appear) stands for Projekt Alphabetisierung und Grundbildung für Erwachsene im Sozialraum (Project Alphabetization and Basic Education for Adults in Social Areas); in addition to language and literacy acquisition the project has also focussed on aspects of adult education and migrational sociology, see project report for details.

2.3 Immigrant learners

As pointed out above, the degrees of oral proficiency in GSL differ greatly among immigrant learners. This is relevant for the situation in literacy classes because it can be observed that those learners who have solid oral skills may have a headstart in the early stages of literacy development over those learners who have very limited command of the spoken language. However, those learners who speak GSL more or less fluently often show numerous errors and fossilized structures which they may transfer into their literacy development, mostly because they “write as they speak” and thus transfer fossilized oral structures into their writing. It is not clear, though, in how far fossilization has an actual impact on their general process of literacy development, this point requires future investigations.

The existing literate skills that immigrant learners dispose of when they start attending a literacy class can be represented on a continuum ranging from those learners who have never read or written a word before to those learners who possess good literacy skills in their L1 which, however, uses a different writing system than German.

These various conditions and prerequisites combine to provide a complex and very heterogeneous situation for groups of immigrant learners that can be represented in the following chart:

	not literate in any language/writing system	literate in the home language/in a different writing system but not in GSL	literate (at least CEF-level A2) in GSL
no oral proficiency in GSL	I	II	III
basic oral proficiency in GSL	IV	V	VI
solid oral proficiency in GSL	VII	VIII	IX

Figure 1: Proficiency profiles of immigrant learners; (figure adapted from: Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge (2009). Konzept für einen bundesweiten Alphabetisierungskurs. Überarbeitete Fassung für 945 UE.)

The chart shows that there are nine potential combinations of skills, each of these with various increments. While the majority of immigrant learners falls in fields I, II, IV and V, i.e. they have no or only basic oral skills in GSL and no literate skills in German but sometimes basic literacy skills in the home language, there are also learners who

have lived in Germany for a long time and possess solid oral skills, albeit with grammatical errors and fossilized structures (Field VII). Learners from Fields VIII and IX are rare and should not, strictly speaking, be placed in a literacy course but rather in an advanced GSL class or alike.

In spite of these different profiles, all these learners are often instructed together in the same group. This situation calls for specific measures of group-internal differentiation and individual ways of support. In order to provide these, detailed assessments and flexible course curricula are necessary.

3 Literacy education

The German Federal Agency for Migration and Refugees has published guidelines for literacy classes representing a framework for the skills and proficiencies that should be achieved in these classes. It is based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEF) (Council of Europe, 2001) and the aim is for the learners to achieve CEF level B1 which is generally seen as the threshold level for independent speakers. However, for literacy skills in particular, level A1 to A2 is aimed at, which entails basic/elementary skills such as filling in registration forms or writing simple postcards as well as reading basic texts like names, familiar words or simple headlines. This apparent paradox between B1 as the general aim and A1/A2 as the particular aim for literacy skills exists because it is the task of this class type, according to the guidelines, to bring the learner closer to functional literacy skills while imparting GSL oral proficiency at the same time. This requirement points out an important fact: insufficient oral skills in GSL and insufficient reading/writing skills are often inseparable and therefore have to be addressed parallel in groups of immigrant learners. Consequently, literacy education for L2 learners is almost never exclusively dedicated to the teaching of reading, writing, sound-letter-correspondences, decoding strategies etc. but always also involves teaching oral GSL.

Therefore, in the first few weeks of class, it needs to be examined in detail what the specific needs of the individual learner are. However, assessment tools that take into account the described heterogeneity of learner profiles and the attested inseparability of proficiencies are scarce. Additionally, administering these assessments requires a solid degree of analytic and linguistic competence on the part of the literacy instructors, something that their academic training often does not sufficiently equip them with.

3.1 Assessment policies

To date, the existing assessment tools and testing instruments for the evaluation of learners' current level of proficiency in literacy skills are not applicable to the heterogeneous groups of learners described above. First and foremost, the existing tools fail to take into account the learners' existing knowledge in their L1, both in speaking and in writing. Also, they consider the learners' oral skills in GSL only to a limited extent. These shortcomings are due mainly to the highly standardized and very rigid nature of those assessment tools. Additionally, many of the assessment tools that

are being used in practice have been developed for the evaluation of children's literacy acquisition and are not suitable for adult learners (cf. Bulut et al., 2010). However, the increasing degree of heterogeneity in literacy classes has necessitated the development of a flexible, adaptive assessment tool that is suited for adult learners and that is applicable to their individual proficiencies and learning aims.

During the last three years, a research group at the University of Cologne has developed such an adaptive assessment tool (see Bulut et al., 2010 for additional information). The test instrument entitled ADISLA³ (Adaptives Instrument zur Schriftsprachdiagnostik von Lernenden in Alphabetisierungskursen – Adaptive Instrument for the Assessment of Literacy Skills of Learners in Literacy Classes) combines the assessment of learners' reading and writing skills, both for learners of German as a First and as a Second Language, with longitudinal proficiency growth analyses and a portfolio component. It is highly flexible and enables the instructor who administers the assessment to proceed to more complex tasks (i. e. to higher levels of proficiency) or to interrupt the assessment procedure at anytime, according to the learner's individual performance. Additionally, the assessment tool contains teaching suggestions and examples of classroom practices and exercises that the instructor can use for the individual learner. It is, hence, a very comprehensive tool that provides support for both learners and instructors.

3.1.1 Teacher assessment

Course placement continues to be one of the most challenging issues in literacy practice. Often times, this placement takes place on the basis of standardized language tests, oral interviews or short reading/writing samples. These strategies can at best provide a cursory glance at a learner's existing skills. This results in the attested heterogeneity of learner groups, where learners with very different levels of proficiency are instructed together, because their competence has initially only been examined in part. For these groups, the ADISLA instrument provides a possibility for the class teacher to achieve a fine-grained and complete picture of a learners' proficiency at the beginning of the learning process.

The assessment can be administered to the individual learner on a one-to-one basis while the rest of the group is working on individual tasks. In addition to an initial evaluation at the beginning of the learning process, the test can also be administered repeatedly during the learning process to reveal the learner's progress and proficiency growth as well as potential learning plateaus. Such repeated diagnostics enable the instructor to adapt his/her teaching practices and class contents to each learner individually and to react immediately if a learner seems to stagnate.

The test ranges from letter recognition and testing the learner's knowledge of the alphabet over sound and grapheme isolation techniques and sound-grapheme correspondences to reading and writing on the word, sentence and text level. In the reading part it also involves the evaluation of text understanding. For GSL learners the test involves a vocabulary check (item-naming via photographs) in order to gain an

³ At present, the assessment instrument is in the final evaluation stage, therefore representative data regarding the instrument's successfulness do not exist yet. The instrument will be made widely available to literacy class providers by the end of 2011.

impression of their oral skills in L2 German. Additionally, GSL learners are asked to complete a questionnaire in their native language to find out to what extent they can master literacy in their L1.

Generally, the test design is impressionistic and it is intended specifically for the class instructor to achieve a detailed impression of each learner's performance. Also, the test is competence-oriented and based on 'can do' statements. This means, the testing procedure can be interrupted at anytime in order to avoid the learner's frustration. It is the principal aim to find out what the learner 'can do', i.e. what s/he is capable of doing with the spoken/written German language, instead of focusing on the learner's deficits, as many traditional testing tools do.

3.1.2 Self-assessment and portfolio work

In addition to the repeated assessments administered by the instructor, ADISLA also contains a portfolio component that fosters the learners' self-assessment. Especially learners with no prior schooling experience exhibit great difficulties in self-reflection upon their learning process. It is common for these learners to set unrealistic goals for themselves ("In three months, I want to be able to read a book") which, in turn, can lead to frustration and eventually to class drop-out. To avoid this, the assessment tool contains a portfolio component where learners can choose their individual aims for the subsequent class segment of, e.g. three months. These aims are then negotiated with the class instructor who can help to moderate them, if necessary, so that they can be realistically achieved within the agreed time span. The instructor can also show learners what steps and learning strategies they can use to achieve their aim, and the learners can subsequently work on these steps independently or with occasional teacher support.

This procedure will over time lead learners to estimate their own proficiency adequately and to set achievable learning aims for themselves that enhance the learning motivation. Also, this leads to a higher level of learner independence, something that adults with no or little schooling experience often lack.

Finally, the portfolio component serves to collect learners' writing samples and class results over the course of time. Whenever a learner reaches a learning plateau or has the impression to stagnate in his/her learning progress, these samples and results in the longitudinal portfolio show the learner how much his/her skills have increased over time. Especially older learners often feel that they forget class contents easily and have to "start from scratch every week". Confronting them with their earliest writing products and comparing them to their current ones visualizes their progress for them and has a very motivating effect.

Both, teacher assessment and self-assessment with the help of a portfolio instrument, should combine to provide a comprehensive picture of the learner's proficiency and literacy growth. The ADISLA instrument provides this combination and it also provides practical help for class instructors because it suggests classroom strategies, tasks and exercises for heterogeneous learner groups. Especially the latter is much needed since the expertise and education of literacy teachers is nearly as diverse as is the makeup of their learner groups.

3.2 Teacher education

"The assessment, especially the literacy component, should always be administered by experienced instructors who have extensive teaching experience in GSL and also abundant proficiency in literacy education." (Konzept für einen bundesweiten Alphabetisierungskurs: p. 40). This claim shows that whoever administers the assessment should also have prior literacy teaching experience. Ideally, these responsibilities should be undertaken by an experienced teacher who is now specialized in assessing and responsible for course placement. Testing and placement should not be the exclusive responsibility of the teachers, although this is often the case in reality. Very often, it becomes the responsibility of the class teacher to evaluate each learner's individual situation, their current level of knowledge and their learning aims. Subsequently, it is also the instructor's responsibility to select the correct type and amount of teaching content and, in the course of the class, to administer repeated assessments to evaluate the learners' progress.

However, when one compares these numerous duties of literacy instructors to the education that most of them have been able to get, it is obvious that many of them lack the sufficient expertise to fulfill all these responsibilities. First and foremost, this is due to the fact that there has not been, until recently, a university degree specifically designed for literacy teachers. Therefore, the educational backgrounds of literacy teachers are very diverse: only some have had some education in GSL, but many have had a teacher education for subjects other than German, or even possess a university degree for an entirely different field, such as pedagogy, social science etc.

So far, this situation has been remedied by additional teacher trainings for teachers who are already in-service, although the funding situation for such additional trainings is poor. It must be pointed out here that many literacy teachers are highly motivated and take these additional trainings on a voluntary basis and without receiving payment for it. In general, the salary situation of the large majority of literacy instructors must be called 'precarious' (cf. Schramm & Roll, 2010: 6), as it is unsteady and often based on non-permanent contracts or short-term fees.

In order to remedy the non-satisfying educational situation, the College of Education in Weingarten, Germany, has started a Master Degree for Literacy and Basic Education in 2009. It is a part-time degree that can be completed in two years on an extra-occupational basis. It is a practice-oriented modular system that aims at increasing the students' analytic competence and the application of their analyses to teaching practices. The study modules are 1. Literacy and Basic Education, 2. Adult Education, 3. Content Skills – Reading and Writing, 4. Content Skills – Basic Education and Employment, 5. Counselling and Assessment, 6. Academic Research. Unfortunately, the tuition fees for this Master Program are high and given the precarious financial situation of many literacy instructors, it is questionable how many of them have the chance to take part in the program. At present, the geographic location of the College of Education also seems to present an additional barrier to accessing the program, therefore, establishing similar programs in other German colleges and universities would be very desirable. Nonetheless, the Master Program closes a much-debated and very important gap in comprehensive literacy education and is a very promising model for future teacher qualifications.

4 *Future perspectives and desiderata*

As this article has shown, much is left to be done on the way to a comprehensive, individual and qualitatively high system of literacy education in Germany. However, during the past four years important changes have been initiated and promising initiatives have been implemented. Improved teacher education and increased access to literacy instruction for all learners continue to be the most pressing demands.

However, the combination of national efforts and the collaboration with other European and international literacy networks, such as LESLLA, strengthen the present endeavours and point out new paths to further improvements in the system.

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